

DASSI DATA ACCESS POLICY

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Policy objectives

Data Archive for Social Sciences in Italy (DASSI) is a research infrastructure aimed at preserving and sharing data produced in the social sciences. This policy explains how to access the data archived and made available to the users. As stated in its Statute, DASSI is primarily aimed at all researchers (academic and non-academic) working in the social sciences, but also at students, teachers, educators, policy makers, managers and practitioners in public administration, entrepreneurs, media representatives, journalists and ordinary citizens who wish to make use of the archived data.

The procedures for accessing these resources reflect the conditions set out in the licence established by the data depositor. DASSI then manages and implements these conditions through a distribution platform based on [Dataverse](#), where its online catalogue is available.

Principles

DASSI shares and promotes the principles of Open Science and seeks to ensure that access to research is continuous, broad and as open as possible.

The archive also operates in accordance with the FAIR principles¹, ensuring that data are persistent over time, always traceable and, if necessary, accessible through an authentication and authorisation system.

Finally, the modalities and procedures of access to the data comply with the indications and guidelines of the European infrastructure CESSDA², of which DASSI is a member. In general, the conditions of access to the archived data are always clearly indicated in the metadata, so that they can be easily identified and retrieved, and are interoperable with other metadata systems³. Metadata published by DASSI are always available under a Creative Commons licence and remain available even if the data are deleted from the catalogue.

¹The acronym FAIR stands for the four principles that research data should respect: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable. For more details see Wilkinson, M., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. *et al.* The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Sci Data* 3, 160018 (2016). DOI:10.1038/sdata.2016.18

²The CESSDA Data Access Policy can be found at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6722000>.

³Specifications for the interoperability of data access conditions developed by CESSDA are available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5554430>

Data access types and procedures

Access to the data is established in agreement with the owner who deposits them in the DASSI archive. In order to access the data, users must accept the terms and conditions of use (licence) established by the owner. To facilitate access, users can accept these conditions with a single click, and the full text of the licence is always available online through a dedicated link.

The following table shows the main characteristics of the different types of access offered by DASSI through its distribution platform:

Type	Definition	Registration	Licences	Access
Open	Free download and click-through terms of use	Not required	Creative Commons	Access is granted to every users
Restricted: request-based access	Secure download upon request and click-through terms of use	Required	<i>Ad hoc</i> licence	Access is granted to every users who have an account in the DASSI repository
Restricted: controlled access	Secure download upon filling out the request form and click-through terms of use	Required	DASSI licence, <i>ad hoc</i> licence	Access is granted to every users who have an account in the DASSI repository and have filled out the request form

In accordance with the principles of Open Science, DASSI works closely with the data owners to reduce barriers to access as much as possible and to encourage full data sharing. For this reason, the archive generally proposes to adopt one of the Creative Commons licences, which allow access to anyone who requests it. If the owner wishes to restrict access to the deposited data, a different licence can be agreed with DASSI. The archive offers the possibility of using its own licence (DASSI licence), which provides for the collection of additional information on the scope of data use by users.

According to the terms of the licence, access can be granted to everyone (*open access*) or only to registered users (*restricted access: request-based*). In the latter case, additional information on the scope of use may be requested (*restricted access: controlled*).

Open Access

In this case, there is no need for the user to register on the distribution platform or to specify the scope of use. The user browses the online catalogue, finds the data of interest and downloads it directly. Before downloading, the user must accept the terms of use, which in these cases always correspond to a Creative Commons licence. For open access data, DASSI can only collect information on the number of downloads made.

Restricted: request-based access

To access the data, the user must be registered on the distribution platform. Once logged in, the user can access the data by clicking on the 'request access' button. No further steps are required, as all registered users are authorised to download. Before downloading the data, the user must accept the terms of use, which depend on the specific licence set by the data owner. In such cases, in addition to the number of downloads made, DASSI may also know which users have accessed the data. In any case, personal data will be treated in accordance with the privacy policy indicated when registering on the distribution platform.

Restricted: controlled access

In this case, the data are not directly accessible through the distribution platform. To gain access, the user must register and fill out an online form that collects additional information about how the data will be used. The form, available through the link provided in the terms of use, requires the user to specify how the data will be used, what outputs are expected, and to identify any collaborators who will have access to the data. Once completed, the DASSI staff will receive the form and, in case of a positive evaluation, will authorise the user to download the data. Before downloading the data, the user must accept the terms of use. In such cases, the terms of use are indicated in the DASSI licence or in the specific licence established by the data owner.

Embargo

For all types of access, the owner of the data may restrict access for a reasonable period of time (*embargo*), not exceeding one year, from the date of deposit of the data. A

message indicating the end date of the embargo will be displayed on the distribution platform and, once this date has passed, users will be able to download the data depending on the type of access established, according to the procedures indicated above.

The original of this document was drawn up in the Italian language. The Italian version is the authentic version and shall prevail over the English version in all matters of interpretation and construction.